

Implementing Process Capability Index (*Cpk*) for Effective Improvement Stability the Case of a Pressing Shop of an Automobile Company

Ghany Radifan Jihadi¹, Caroline Veda Pangemanan²

^{1,2}Magister of Management Program, Faculty of Economics and Business, Widyatama University, Bandung, Indonesia.

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 12 February 2026</p>	<p>Sheet metal forming, a sheet metal that has a basic shape, is formed between dies to obtain a part with relatively complex geometry with targeted measurement result (tolerance & dimensions). Sheet metal forming produces scraps and generates the final part product in fast paced production, usually in one stroke or a few strokes of press between upper and lower dies ⁽¹⁾. Sheet forming process can offer potential savings in energy and materials in mass production system.</p> <p>Sheet metal forming is in press production shop (stamping) in our company. There are 3 lines of press shop 2000-ton, 1200 ton, and 500 ton. Each produces about 1000 parts per day. The dimension of the finished product should be in the desired tolerance and measurement. Inconsistent product dimensions will result in inaccurate results of the whole product at welding and assembly shop.</p> <p>Capability of process (e.g. <i>Cp</i>, <i>Cpk</i>, and <i>CPM</i>) calculating dimension variability to drawing, with <i>Cpk</i> used to focus on centering the process mean with the specification / drawing center ^(1, 2, 3). In this paper we analyze quality stabilization of improvement part by using <i>Cpk</i> to analyze whether improvement process data are accurate and stable. Process capability (<i>Cpk</i>) calculates and compared before and after adjusting the parameters for selected dimensions within part for measurement (based on drawing), employing an image measuring instrument for collecting 30 units data before improvement and 30 units data after improvement and makes the conclusion based on the <i>Cpk</i> result.</p>
<p>Corresponding Author: Ghany Radifan Jihadi</p>	
<p>KEYWORDS: Precision Manufacturing, Process Capability Index (<i>Cpk</i>), Quality Improvement, Production Stability</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry operates in a competitive environment with a challenge to make a product which is low cost, high quality and on-time delivery. In a manufacturing operation, raising the capability process (*Cpk*) in one of production lines (press part, weld part, painting, etc.) can be the performance determinant of the whole process ⁽⁴⁾. Therefore, the manufacturing process needs the capable process. Capability process is called *Cp*, *Cpk*, and *CPM* and the purpose of this method is to calculate is the subject of the calculation is capable or not capable. To gain capable process, there should be effort to gain high accuracy and high precision in the process ⁽⁵⁾

Process planning and process capability are always connected and have played a pivotal role in manufacturing ⁽⁶⁾. Process planning involves many things, including machinery, tools, equipment, and manpower. Besides planning, measuring instruments and materials, as well as the skills and training needed for the personnel involved in the production

process are needed. Process capability, on the other hand, analyzes and evaluates the different variations in process planning, using statistical indices, to ensure that the selected optimal process plan provides efficient manufacturing and high-quality products, as required in responsible industries such as automotive ⁽³⁾. High accuracy and high precision are needed to gain capable production. Accurate within the dimension tolerance and precise within dimension and centered.

Fig 1. (a) Accurate within tolerance dimensions, but not precise (b) Precise within the drawing tolerance dimensions but not accurate ⁽¹⁰⁾.

Understanding processes and calculating *Cpk* performance are important for any successful quality improvement program. The relationship between actual process performance and specification limits or tolerances can be calculated using *Cpk*. In the manufacturing industry, three commonly used capability indices are the Process Capability Index (*Cp*), the process capability index with centering (*Cpk*), and the process Capability Index with target (*Cpm*) ⁽³⁾. In manufacturing industry, *Cpk* is the most used process capability index ^(4 – 8).

II. DATA, MATERIAL, AND METHODE

Established in 1990, the automotive company specialized in production of automobile, motorbike,ATV , and outboard machine. It provides customers with various product choices. The company has a total capacity of 300,000 unit/year (combined factory capacity). The factory located in Indonesia. The company export the vehicle across the ASEAN and south America. The main production process is pressing (stamping), welding, painting, and assembling shop. In this paper, we focus on the pressing (stamping) shop 2. Pressing shop consists of 3 big press machines. (1) 2000 tons, (2) 1200 tons, and (3) 500 tons. This pressing machine is used to make automobile components to be assembled in welding shop and then become white body. The focus in this paper is to measure the *Cpk* of the *Frame Floor, Front* part after improvement the 2000 tons press machine.

II.1 MEASUREMENT OBJECTIVE AND METHODS

The actual part is measured at 3 points (based on 3D data) by using hexagon absolute arm (fig 3). The measured data total is 60 units. 30 units measured before improvement, and 30 units after improvement. The sample part before improvement is produced one day before the improvement part produced. The measurement is conducted by a certified quality staff member.

Fig.2 Part Frame Floor, Front

Measurement method is using coordinate-based 3D color maps to allow visualization of the 3D scene geometry depicted in overlapping images that described, followed by a presentation of stages of automatic multi-image reconstructions, conventional photogrammetric procedure ⁽⁷⁾. The image that was produced by the CMM (fig.3) displays the differences between measured part and the 3D model (fig.4).

Fig.3 Coordinated Measuring Machine (CMM)

Hexagon Absolute Arm 7 Axis 0 -3500 mm

Fig.4. Color mapping measurement and image of 3 points (position) for calculating *Cpk* .

Within the tolerance of ± 1.2 mm (minimal value -1.2 and maximum value +1.2 mm). The measured 3 points data is collected for 30 units sample to count the *Cpk* before improvement and 30 units after improvement. The sample part before improvement is produced a day before the sample part for improvement.

II.2 EQUATION

Capability process (*Cpk*) as the indicator process capability (2). *Cpk* is a critical quantitative method in statistical process control (SPC) used to measure whether a process can produce accurate and precise output. *Cpk* value if <1.00 the process is not capable, *Cpk* = 1.00 is barely capable, *Cpk* = 1.33 minimum acceptable in many industries (capable process and good for mass production), *Cpk* = 1.67 highly capable, and *Cpk* >2.00 is world class (12).

$$Cpk = \min \frac{USL - \bar{x}}{3\sigma}, \frac{\bar{x} - LSL}{3\sigma} \quad (1)$$

Where \bar{x} is the mean of the sample data (process mean) and σ is the standard deviation of the sample data. Calculating *Cpk* is to measure the distance from \bar{x} to nearest specification limit, reflecting whether the process mean deviate from the target specification. In practical quality control process, the *x*-bar chart (\bar{x} – chart) and range control chart (*R*-chart) are used to visualize the result of sample measurement (12).

In application, the *x*-bar chart (\bar{x} – chart) and range control chart (*R*-chart) are used to display the result of sample measurements (2,11,12,13). For example, as shown on Fig.5, the \bar{x} display the variation of the 30 units sample measurement before improvements. The *x* chart consists of UCL (upper control limit) and LCL (lower control limit), defined as minimum tolerance -1.2 mm and maximum tolerance +1.2 mm, because the specification (drawing) mentions that the tolerance of ±1.2 mm is acceptable.

II.2 METHOD OF CAPABILITY PROCESS (*C_{PK}*) CALCULATION

The purpose of *Cpk* calculation in this study is to compare the *Cpk* calculation before and after improvement at pressing (stamp) shop. Process flow for this paper *Cpk* calculation is written below.

Fig. 5 Process flow for *Cpk* comparison before and after improvement

III. RESULT

After measuring the sample part before and after improvement at 3 points surface based on the drawing. Control chart display is using upper control level (UCL) and lower control level (LCL) using tolerance drawing dimensions. Maximum value (UCL) is +1.2 mm and minimum value (LCL) is -1.2 mm. Capability process (*Cpk*) as the indicator process capability (2). *Cpk* is a critical quantitative method in statistical process control (SPC) used to measure whether a process can produce accurate and precise output. *Cpk* value if <1.00 the process is not capable, *Cpk* = 1.00 is barely capable, *Cpk* = 1.33 minimum acceptable in many industries (capable process and good for mass production), *Cpk* = 1.67 highly capable, and *Cpk* >2.00 is world class (12).

III.1 CALCULATING CPK BEFORE IMPROVEMENT

Capability process (*Cpk*) as the indicator process capability (2). *Cpk* is a critical quantitative method in statistical process control (SPC) used to measure whether a process can produce accurate and precise output. *Cpk* value if <1.00 the process is not capable, *Cpk* = 1.00 is barely capable, *Cpk* = 1.33 minimum acceptable in many industries (capable process and good for mass production), *Cpk* = 1.67 highly capable, and *Cpk* >2.00 is world class (12).

$$Cpk = \min \frac{USL - \bar{x}}{3\sigma}, \frac{\bar{x} - LSL}{3\sigma} \quad (1)$$

Where \bar{x} is the mean of the sample data (process mean) and σ is the standard deviation of the sample data. Calculating *Cpk* is to measure the distance from \bar{x} to nearest specification limit, reflecting whether the process mean deviate from the target specification. In practical quality control process, the *x*-bar chart (\bar{x} – chart) and range control chart (*R*-chart) are used to visualize the result of sample measurement (12).

In application, the *x*-bar chart (\bar{x} – chart) and range control chart (*R*-chart) are used to display the result of sample measurements (2,11,12,13). For example, as shown on Fig.5, the \bar{x} display the variation of the 30 units sample measurement before improvements. The *x* chart consists of UCL (upper control limit) and LCL (lower control limit), defined as minimum tolerance -1.2 mm and maximum tolerance +1.2 mm, because the specification (drawing) mentions that the tolerance of ±1.2 mm is acceptable.

“Influence Transformational Leadership , Strategic Policy , and Knowledge Management on the Organizational Performance of the Army Headquarters Mediated by Organizational Commitment”

Fig 6. \bar{x} chart for the Cpk data before part improvement in the case study. UCL : Upper Control Limit (Tolerance), LCL : Lower Control Limit (tolerance), CL : Center Line (tolerance)

Table 1. Capability process (Cpk), x (Before)

Item	Cpk
Point 1	2.07
Point 2	1.78
Point 3	1.04

III.2 CALCULATING Cpk AFTER IMPROVEMENT

After improvement, the sample part produces 30 units to calculate the Cpk result. The measurement device, the operator and the method is same as before. The sample part is produced on the same day (same as before). The purpose of the calculation is to check whether Cpk of the improvement is accurate and precision as before.

Fig 7. \bar{x} chart for the Cpk data after part improvement in the case study. UCL : Upper Control Limit, LCL : Lower Control Limit, CL : Center Line

Table 2. Capability process (Cpk), x (After)

Item	After
Point 1	1.17
Point 2	1.73
Point 3	1.11

III.3 COMPARING THE RESULT

After measuring the parts before and after the improvement and gaining the Cpk result. The result is shown at the table below

Table 3. Capability process (Cpk), x (After)

Item	Before	After
Point 1	2.07	1.17
Point 2	1.78	1.73
Point 3	1.04	1.11

After comparing the Cpk result from 3 points of measurement before and after improvement. The results are (1) point 1 Cpk result is lowered from 2.07 to 1.17, (2) point 2 Cpk also reduced from 1.78 to 1.73, and (3) point 3 raise a little from 1.04 to 1.11. The meaning of the result are (1) The improvement process of point 1 and 2 has lower Cpk result from before. (2) Therefore point 1 and point 3 is barely capable, maintenance should be conducted to improve the machine condition. Only point 2 that is higher than the standard Cpk of 1.3

IV. SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

Automotive industry is facing the challenge of making high quality products and minimizing costs to survive in these times. Quality defective products will consume big amount of company profit. Therefore, any improvement of the process must be calculated to high accuracy and precise measurements. If the improvement results are only approved by only 1 (one) sample, we cannot guarantee that the improvement will be accurate and precise in the future. Therefore, Cpk must be used to calculate whether the improvement is making high accuracy and precise part for mass production.

The relationship between “precision and accurate” Cpk is significant important both theoretically and practically, primarily involving how precise process control can achieve consistent and high-quality product output. The improvement changes the Cpk of point 1 is lowered from 2.07 to 1.17, (2) point 2 Cpk also reduced from 1.78 to 1.73, and (3) point 3 raise a little from 1.04 to 1.11

This result showed that the improved process Cpk value is lower overall than before, therefore maintenance and adjustment should be done in the 2000-ton press machine. Suggestion for next research is to calculate Cpk again after improvement has been conducted. If the Cpk result after maintenance is better, therefore we can say that the

“Influence Transformational Leadership , Strategic Policy , and Knowledge Management on the Organizational Performance of the Army Headquarters Mediated by Organizational Commitment”

improvement can make high accuracy and precise product. If the *Cpk* value is lowered again after improvement, the maintenance process maybe in the other parts in the machine.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to all individuals who contributed to this research, either directly or indirectly. Their valuable discussions, feedback, and support greatly assisted in the completion of this study.

REFERENCES

1. Taylan Altan and A.Erman Tekkaya: Sheet metal forming. August 2012 ASM International
2. Teng-Hsiung Lin, Lan-Chien Huang, Yue-Yang Chen,Liang-Cheng Lee,5 and Dyi-Yih Michael Lin. Implementing Process Capability Index (*Cpk*) for Effective Product Quality Stabilization: The Case of a Lock Manufacturing Company (June 2024). SM3982.pdf
3. Tanya Avramova Dimka Vasileva, Teodora Peneva. An Overview of the basic concepts and terms related to manufacturing process capability evaluation. An overview of the basic concepts and terms related to manufacturing process capability evaluation | AIP Conference Proceedings | AIP Publishing.
4. Kuen-Suan Chen, Kung-Jeng Wang & Tsang-Chuan Chang. A novel approach to deriving the lower confidence limit of indices *Cpu*, *Cpl*, and *Cpk* in assessing process capability (March 2017). A novel approach to deriving the lower confidence limit of indices *Cpu*, *Cpl*, and *Cpk* in assessing process capability: International Journal of Production Research: Vol 55, No 17
5. Luis Alberto Rodríguez-Picón, Luis Carlos Méndez-González, Victor Hugo Flores-Ochoa & Manuel Arnoldo Rodríguez-Medina . Capability indices for circular tolerance regions based on a gaussian copula (August-2019). Capability indices for circular tolerance regions based on a Gaussian copula | The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology | Springer Nature Link
6. Siim Koppel, Shing I. Chang. A process capability analysis method using adjusted modified sample entropy (2016). A Process Capability Analysis Method Using Adjusted Modified Sample Entropy - ScienceDirect
7. Styliani Verykokou and Charalabos Ioannidis. An overview on Image Based and Scanner Based 3D modelling technologies (January 2023). An Overview on Image-Based and Scanner-Based 3D Modeling Technologies | MDPI
8. Y. Yang: Recent Dev. Mech. Intell. Robot. **415** (2019) 415. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-00214-5_53
9. W. L. Pearn and P. Lin: Comput. Ind. Eng. 47 (2004) 351. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2003.03.001>
10. Rahtomo, Wahyu. 2019. Statistical process control. Productivity & Quality Management Consultants.
11. Automotive Industri Action Group, (1995) Advanced Product Quality planning and control plan; Reference manual
12. Automotive Industry Action Group, (1995) Statistical Process Control
13. K. Palmer and K.-L. Tsui: Ann. Oper. Res. 87 (1999) 31. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1018993221702>
14. Forman, G. (2003). An extensive empirical study of feature selection metrics for text classification. Journal of Machine Learning Research, 3(Mar), 1289–1305.
15. Fröhlich, B., & Plate, J. (2000). The cubic mouse: A new device for three-dimensional input. In Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (pp. xx–xx). New York, NY: ACM Press.
16. Bowman, M., Debray, S. K., & Peterson, L. L. (1993). Reasoning about naming systems. ACM Transactions on Programming Languages and Systems, 15(5), 795–825.

Appendix 1. Data Before Improvement

Sample No	Point 1	Point 2	Point 3	UCL	LCL
1	-0.795	-0.402	-0.897	1.2	-1.2
2	-0.662	-0.525	-0.821	1.2	-1.2
3	-0.898	-0.431	-0.767	1.2	-1.2
4	-0.623	-0.455	-0.838	1.2	-1.2
5	-0.757	-0.325	-0.901	1.2	-1.2
6	-0.851	-0.199	-0.911	1.2	-1.2
7	-0.711	-0.325	-0.941	1.2	-1.2
8	-0.603	-0.455	-0.705	1.2	-1.2
9	-0.654	-0.325	-0.54	1.2	-1.2
10	-0.82	-0.601	-0.777	1.2	-1.2
11	-0.703	-0.455	-0.808	1.2	-1.2
12	-0.772	-0.425	-0.722	1.2	-1.2
13	-0.613	-0.524	-0.922	1.2	-1.2
14	-0.812	-0.322	-0.718	1.2	-1.2
15	-0.704	-0.188	-0.567	1.2	-1.2
16	-0.831	-0.845	-0.953	1.2	-1.2
17	-0.647	-0.129	-0.851	1.2	-1.2
18	-0.754	-0.122	-0.55	1.2	-1.2
19	-0.767	-0.203	-0.735	1.2	-1.2
20	-0.712	-0.322	-0.923	1.2	-1.2
21	-0.664	-0.233	-0.754	1.2	-1.2
22	-0.678	-0.315	-0.878	1.2	-1.2
23	-0.751	-0.525	-0.877	1.2	-1.2

“Influence Transformational Leadership , Strategic Policy , and Knowledge Management on the Organizational Performance of the Army Headquarters Mediated by Organizational Commitment”

24	-0.694	-0.302	-0.878	1.2	-1.2
25	-0.712	-0.355	-0.763	1.2	-1.2
26	-0.797	-0.2	-0.519	1.2	-1.2
27	-0.807	-0.555	-0.931	1.2	-1.2
28	-0.69	-0.423	-0.947	1.2	-1.2
29	-0.721	-0.401	-0.909	1.2	-1.2
30	-0.805	-0.302	-0.744	1.2	-1.2

Appendix 2. Data After Improvement

After

Sample No	Point 1	Point 2	Point 3	UCL	LCL
1	-0.387	-0.46	-0.757	1.2	-1.2
2	-0.32	-0.264	-0.532	1.2	-1.2
3	-0.29	0.31	-0.71	1.2	-1.2
4	-0.431	-0.321	-0.477	1.2	-1.2
5	-0.302	-0.527	-0.572	1.2	-1.2
6	-0.23	-0.313	-0.654	1.2	-1.2
7	-0.35	-0.433	-0.761	1.2	-1.2
8	-0.287	-0.274	-0.581	1.2	-1.2
9	-0.306	-0.212	-0.55	1.2	-1.2
10	-0.202	-0.156	-0.451	1.2	-1.2
11	-0.311	-0.487	-0.567	1.2	-1.2
12	-0.254	-0.338	-0.505	1.2	-1.2
13	-0.453	-0.372	-0.676	1.2	-1.2
14	-0.433	-0.361	-0.422	1.2	-1.2
15	-0.503	-0.412	-0.644	1.2	-1.2
16	-0.381	-0.122	-0.583	1.2	-1.2
17	-0.499	-0.432	-0.861	1.2	-1.2
18	-0.401	-0.377	-0.551	1.2	-1.2
19	-0.592	-0.359	-0.705	1.2	-1.2
20	-0.485	-0.111	-0.48	1.2	-1.2
21	-0.397	-0.435	-0.766	1.2	-1.2
22	-0.378	-0.282	-0.878	1.2	-1.2
23	-0.451	-0.542	-0.877	1.2	-1.2
24	-0.394	-0.338	-0.878	1.2	-1.2
25	-0.412	-0.373	-0.763	1.2	-1.2
26	-0.45	-0.173	-0.519	1.2	-1.2
27	-0.507	-0.511	-0.931	1.2	-1.2
28	-0.39	-0.454	-0.947	1.2	-1.2
29	-0.421	-0.451	-0.909	1.2	-1.2
30	0.85	-0.356	-0.744	1.2	-1.2